

SOP 01. Fungal growth and storage

Objective: To outline the procedures for the long-term storage and cultivation of edible fungi mycelium.

Materials:

- Petri dishes
- Sterile MicroSac (<https://saco2.com/>)
- Sterile spatula
- Sterile scalpes
- Sterile 100 ul tips
- Sterile 10 ml tips
- Storage refrigerator (set to 2°C)
- Incubator (set to 25°C)
- Liquid culture medium
- 300 ml sterile bottles
- PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar)
- Centrifuge
- BSG (Brewer's Spent Grain)
- PDB (Potato Dextrose Broth)

Petri dishes for long storage:

1. Inoculation and initial growth:

- In the food grade microbiological hood, inoculate edible fungi mycelium in Petri dishes using ~1 cm² of agar mycelium (see SOP 2 for further details)
- Place the inoculated Petri dishes into SacO2 bags and seal using the food vacuum pump set at 1 sec vacuum (Komet, Vacuboy)

2. Long-term storage:

- grow the fungi at 25°C to increase the available mycelium example of grown fungi ready for storage.

- Store the sealed SacO2 bags at 2°C for 8-10 months

Example:

Liquid culture for long storage:

1. Liquid media inoculation:

- In the food grade microbiological hood, inoculate edible fungi mycelium in 170 ml of sterile PDB using ~2 x 1 cm² of agar mycelium.
- Grow inoculated liquid culture at 25 °C aiming to obtain (0.003 g dry matter/ml).
- Break the mycelium daily by vigorously shaking it for one minute.
- Place the grown liquid culture at 10°C for storage of up to 1 month.
- Agitate flasks at least once per week to increase available oxygen.

2. Viability Check:

- Agitate the solution to ensure mycelium sampling. In food grade microbiological hood plate 100 µl of liquid culture suspension on PDA to check if the mycelium is alive and contamination occurred.

Examples:

3. Inoculum Preparation:

- In food grade microbiological hood sample 30 ml of inoculum suspension into a sterile falcon (50 ml red cap).
- Centrifuge the inoculum suspension (e.g., 30 ml for 300g of hydrated BSG) at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes at 20°C.
- Discard the supernatant to avoid metabolite toxicity, avoid discarding mycelia.
- Substitute the supernatant with the same amount of fresh PDB.
- Incubate the inoculum for two days at 25°C before inoculating into BSG. Shake daily.

SOP 02. Inoculation of Petri Dishes and PDB with Fungal Mycelia

Objective: provide a standardized method for inoculating Petri dishes and Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB) with fungal mycelia for consistent and reproducible growth.

Materials and Equipment:

- Sterile scalpel
- Petri dishes with fresh Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA)
- Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB)
- Grown fungal mycelia on agar
- 300 ml sterilized glass bottles
- Glass beads 3 mm diameter (5.5 g per bottle)
- Magnetic stirrer
- Parafilm
- Incubator set to 25°C
- Microbiological hood

Procedure:

1. Preparation:

- Ensure all materials are sterilized and ready for use.
- Use dry sterilization procedure for empty glass bottles filled with glass beads and magnetic stirrer. Use wet sterilization procedures for PDB and PDA
- Plate PDA at 60°C under microbiological hood. Dry well the plates to avoid condensation droplets.
- Perform all operations under a microbiological hood to maintain sterility.

2. Inoculation of Petri Dishes:

- Use a sterile scalpel to cut 1 cm square cubes of agar containing fungal mycelia.

Example: cut of 1 cm square cubes of viable mycelia

- Select apical mycelia, as it is the most metabolically active.
- Flip the 1 cm square agar cubes onto the fresh PDA in the Petri dishes.
- Ensure the agar squares are placed centrally on the PDA surface.

3. Inoculation of PDB:

- Cut two 1 cm square agar cubes with fungal mycelia.
- Within these squares, cut smaller pieces to increase mycelia dispersion.
- Pour 170 ml of PDB into the bottle in a sterile environment.
- Add the cut mycelia to the PDB.
- Close the bottle and seal it with parafilm.

4. Incubation:

- Incubate the 300 ml bottle at 24°C under continuous stirring.

Example of grown mycelia:

- Shake vigorously once a day to break the mycelium.

Example of broken mycelium.

N.B. expect a difference in mycelium behavior in liquid culture.

Safety and Precautions:

- Always work under a microbiological hood to maintain a sterile environment.
- Use personal protective equipment (PPE), including gloves and lab coat.
- Handle sharp instruments with care to avoid injury.

SOP 03. Inoculum preparation for solid substrate fermentation

Objective: provide a standardized method for preparing the inoculum for the BSG

Materials and Equipment:

- Liquid fungal culture
- PDB
- 10 ml pipette
- 50 ml sterile Falcon tube (red cap)
- 15 ml sterile Falcon tube
- Centrifuge
- Sterile water
- Personal protective equipment (PPE): gloves and lab coat
- Microbiological hood
- Moisture analyzer (MA30 Sartorius, Goettingen, Germany)

Procedure:

- 1. Preparation:**
 - Perform this procedure only on the day of the inoculation.
 - Perform all operations with open liquid culture or falcon under a microbiological hood to maintain sterility.
- 2. Sampling inoculum:**
 - Shake the liquid fungal culture to ensure homogeneity of the mycelia.
 - Using a 10 ml pipette, transfer 30 ml of the mycelia culture into a 50 ml sterile Falcon tube (red cap).
 - Sample 5 ml of the culture and transfer it into a 15 ml Falcon tube. Sample 5 ml of sterile PDB in another falcon. These samples will be dried to test the growth of the mycelia.
- 3. Centrifugation:**
 - Centrifuge the 50 ml Falcon tube at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes at 20°C.
 - Carefully remove the supernatant in a sterile environment without discarding the mycelia. Note that some media may remain in the Falcon tube.
- 4. Mycelia Resuspension:**
 - Add 30 ml of sterile water to the mycelia in the Falcon tube.
 - Manually shake the Falcon tube to resuspend the mycelia thoroughly.
 - Store at room temperature until use.
- 5. Moisture analysis:**
 - Use the moisture analyzer to analyze the moisture of the sterilized media and the inoculum to understand the dry matter of the inoculum (40 min per analysis)
 - Weight the sample and write the initial weight to calculate the dry matter.

SOP 04. Box sterilization and BSG pasteurization

Objective: ensure microbiological sterility and correct handling of materials and BSG

Materials and Equipment:

- SacO2 boxes with green filter (81.35 Gas Exchange/day) (SacO2, Deinze, Belgium)
- Kitchen aid (Chef XL KVL4100S, Kenwood Ltd, Hampshire United Kingdom)
- Whisk for Kitchen aid
- Silicone spatula
- Vacuum bags
- Water
- BSG flour (Circular Food Technology ApS, Copenhagen, Denmark)
- Balance
- Vacuum pump (Vacuboy, Komet, Germany)
- Oven (iCombi, Rotational, Germany)

Procedure:

1. SacO2 boxes sterilization:

- Use dry sterilization procedure to sterilize the boxes prior to usage.
- Partially close the boxes as shown in the picture (left).

- Use roll bags to seal the boxes from the external environment.
- #### 2. BSG handling from 10 kg bags (average particle size 190µm):
- Mix the bag while closed.
 - Open the bag and mix it with a big metal spoon.
 - Sample ~1.5 kg of BSG into plastic boxes.
 - Place plastic film (to avoid oxidation) and close with lid. Label according to example

Example:

3. BSG hydration:

- In Gastro science lab C022. Mix the flour while closed.
- Use the proportion to obtain hydrated BSG amounts.

$$X_{\text{total amount BSG}} : Y_{100+\text{hydration}} = X_{\text{water to add}} : \text{Hydration}$$

Example for 150% hydration:

$$1300\text{g} : 250 = X : 150$$

$$X_{\text{water to add}} = 780\text{g} ; X_{\text{BSG}} = 1300 - 780 = 520\text{g}$$

- Pour the flour into the kitchen aid. Attach the whisk and select the speed 3. Pour slowly the water while whisking. When incorporated, increase the speed up to the maximum.

Example kitchen aid:

- Stop the KitchenAid mixer. Using a silicone spatula, mix the bottom of the KitchenAid bowl well. Whisk at high speed to reincorporate the mixture.
- Weight 300g of mixture in long vacuum bags and label the hydration level.

Example:

- Heat the kitchen oven to 90°C using only steam and full fan.
- Seal the vacuum bags using the vacuum pump set to 12 seconds to ensure a 99% vacuum. Carefully inspect the sealing site; if it is not completely sealed, repeat the procedure. Avoid wrinkles that could lead to contamination post-treatment.
- Using perforated trays place the seal BSG bags into the oven. Pasteurize for 25 minutes.
- After the pasteurization chill the sealed bags in cold water, until room temperature.
- Use the pasteurized BSG or store it in the fridge for a maximum of 24 hours (aimed to avoid LAB proliferation).

SOP 05. BSG inoculation and incubation

Objective: ensure mycelia development in BSG while avoiding contamination

Materials and Equipment:

- Sterile SacO2 boxes with green filter (81.35 Gas Exchange/day) (SacO2, Deinze, Belgium)
- Kitchen aid (Chef XL KVL4100S, Kenwood Ltd, Hampshire United Kingdom)
- Whisk for Kitchen aid
- Silicone spatula
- Metal spatula
- Metal bowl
- Pasteurized BSG (at room temperature)
- 30 ml inoculum or sterile water (for 10% v/w)
- Spray bottle with ethanol solution 70%
- Cleaning paper
- Cleaning towel

- Gloves and disposable apron
- Portable Bunsen
- Incubator (Termark 600, LH Laboratory Service, Denmark)
- Humidifier (Ultrasonic Humidifier, China)

Procedure:

1. Preparation of the Lab Environment:

- Minimize contamination from aerosols and suspended particulates.
- Clean all tables and surfaces in the laboratory with a 1% HCl solution.
- Follow up by cleaning the tables and surfaces with a 70% ethanol solution.

2. Cleaning and Preparing Equipment:

- Clean the KitchenAid mixer with a 70% ethanol solution.
- Pasteurize the KitchenAid bowl and whisk in the dishwasher (average 80C per 10 min).
- Dry the KitchenAid bowl and whisk thoroughly.
- Place the whisk into the KitchenAid bowl and spray with a 70% ethanol solution.
- Place the silicone spatula in the metal bowl and clean with a 70% ethanol solution.
- Turn on the portable Bunsen burner and place it next to the KitchenAid mixer.
- Dry all utensils with cleaning paper.

3. Handling and Mixing the Material:

- Open one sealed bag of BSG and pour it into the bowl of the KitchenAid mixer.
- Set the KitchenAid mixer to speed 3 to break up the material.
- Gradually increase the speed to homogenize the material thoroughly.
- Decrease the speed to 2 and slowly pour in the mycelia suspended in water.
- Increase the speed for 30 seconds to mix.
- Turn off the KitchenAid mixer and use the silicone spatula to further homogenize the material manually.
- Resume mixing with the KitchenAid at speed 3 for better homogenization.

4. Transferring and Leveling the Material:

- Pour the homogenized BSG into sterile SacO₂ boxes.
- Use a metal spatula to level the material as demonstrated in the example.

Example 150% hydration:

Example 200% hydration:

- Seal the box and label it paper with paper scotch. Place it in the incubator in the basement. Set humidifier to mist 2 (~200 ml/h). Check daily.

5. Cleaning and Sterilizing for the Next Inoculation:

- Before proceeding with the next inoculation, pasteurize and clean all equipment.
- Spray all surfaces and materials with a 70% ethanol solution.

SOP 06. Fungal “dry” fermentation

Objective: develop additional aroma flavor through concentration and secondary metabolism of the mycelia

Materials and Equipment:

- Incubator without humidifier

Test samples presented a complex mushroom profile. The conditions for growth were 25C and relative humidity of 73-80% from day 1 to day 8. On the 8th day the relative humidity was diminished to 47% RH average.